

Marketing

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Marketing and advertising strategies for business expansion in emerging markets: integrating outdoor media for maximum reach

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Abstract. The **purpose** of this study is a comprehensive analysis of marketing and advertising strategies that contribute to the effective expansion of business in developing markets, with a special emphasis on integrating outdoor advertising with other marketing channels. It ensures maximum coverage of the target audience, increases brand recognition and strengthens the competitive position of enterprises.

Methods. The work uses a systematic approach that combines the analysis of traditional and digital advertising methods, considering the socio-cultural, economic, technological and demographic characteristics of specific markets. The research methods used include comparative analysis, expert assessment, content analysis, and quantitative and qualitative methods for assessing the effectiveness of various communication channels: television, radio, print media, mobile marketing, outdoor advertising, social networks and direct activity. Special attention is paid to analyzing the conditions of limited digital infrastructure, which is characteristic of many developing countries. **Results.** It was found that integrating outdoor advertising with other marketing tools significantly increases brand awareness,

creates a positive image, and contributes to effective customer attraction and retention. A key factor in success is the adaptation of advertising messages to the local context, which includes language, cultural values, traditions, social norms, and consumer behavior. Considering these aspects allows you to create more relevant, targeted, and attractive advertising campaigns. In situations where digital presence is limited, combined strategies that combine outdoor advertising with mobile marketing, local radio, and print media are particularly effective. The results obtained can serve as the basis for further scientific research in the field of marketing and advertising in emerging markets, as well as for the development of practical recommendations and strategies for small and medium-sized businesses seeking to enter new markets, taking into account local characteristics, challenges, and limitations. The **conclusions** of this study hold both theoretical and practical significance, forming a basis for future scholarly contributions and serving as practical guidelines for SMEs aiming to effectively expand into new markets under conditions of limited resources and heterogeneous media environments.

Keywords: communication strategies, market potential, advertising effectiveness, integrated communications, consumer loyalty, digital transformation, market entry barriers.

**Маркетингові та рекламні стратегії для розширення бізнесу на ринках,
що розвиваються: інтеграція зовнішньої реклами для максимального
охоплення**

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Анотація. Метою цього дослідження є комплексний аналіз маркетингових і рекламних стратегій, які сприяють ефективному розширенню бізнесу на ринках, що розвиваються, з особливим акцентом на інтеграцію зовнішньої реклами з іншими маркетинговими каналами. Це дозволяє забезпечити максимальне охоплення цільової аудиторії, підвищити впізнаваність бренду та посилити конкурентні позиції підприємств. **Методи.** У роботі застосовано системний підхід, що поєднує аналіз традиційних та цифрових методів реклами з урахуванням соціокультурних, економічних, технологічних і демографічних особливостей конкретних ринків. Використовувані методи дослідження включають порівняльний аналіз, експертну оцінку, контент-аналіз, а також кількісні та якісні методи оцінки ефективності різних каналів комунікації: телебачення, радіо, друкованих засобів масової інформації, мобільного маркетингу, зовнішньої реклами, соціальних мереж та прямої активності. Особливу увагу приділено аналізу умов обмеженої цифрової інфраструктури, що є характерними для багатьох країн, що розвиваються. **Результати.** Виявлено, що інтеграція зовнішньої реклами з іншими маркетинговими інструментами суттєво підвищує впізнаваність бренду, формує позитивний імідж, а також сприяє ефективному залученню та утриманню клієнтів. Ключовим фактором успіху є адаптація рекламних повідомлень до локального контексту, що включає мову, культурні цінності, традиції, соціальні норми та поведінкові особливості споживачів. Врахування цих аспектів дозволяє створювати більш релевантні, цілеспрямовані та привабливі рекламні кампанії. У ситуаціях, коли цифрова присутність обмежена, особливо ефективними виявляються комбіновані стратегії, що поєднують зовнішню рекламу з мобільним маркетингом, місцевим радіо та друкованими ЗМІ. Отримані результати можуть слугувати основою для подальших наукових досліджень у сфері маркетингу та реклами на ринках, що розвиваються, а також для розробки практичних рекомендацій

і стратегій для малого та середнього бізнесу, який прагне вийти на нові ринки, враховуючи локальні особливості, виклики та обмеження. **Висновки** дослідження мають як теоретичну, так і прикладну значущість: вони формують основу для подальших наукових напрацювань у сфері реклами на ринках, що розвиваються, а також слугують практичними орієнтирами для малого та середнього бізнесу, що прагне ефективно освоювати нові ринки в умовах обмежених ресурсів і неоднорідного медіасередовища.

Ключові слова: комунікаційні стратегії, ринковий потенціал, ефективність реклами, інтегровані комунікації, споживча лояльність, цифрова трансформація, бар'єри виходу на ринок.

Problem statement. In the current conditions of globalization and digital transformation, developed countries actively focus on developing markets as a promising direction for business expansion. At the same time, a compelling presence in these markets is complicated by communication barriers associated with limited access to digital communication channels and the specifics of local consumer behavior. It necessitates the need for flexible marketing approaches that can adapt to the specifics of the environment. In such conditions, outdoor advertising remains effective in reaching a broad audience, especially in regions with insufficient Internet coverage. The problem lies in the lack of scientifically sound approaches to integrating outdoor advertising into marketing strategies for developing markets and the limited empirical research on its effectiveness. Studying this issue is essential both for developing the theory of marketing communications and for creating practical recommendations for the effective use of outdoor media in conditions of limited resources and high competition.

Analysis of recent research and publications. At the theoretical level, the research of V. V. Bilyk, O. A. Serhienko and I. A. Krupenna [1] is essential, where a typology of digital marketing tools in the context of business communication

adaptation is formed, which allows for a deeper understanding of transformational processes in the field of advertising. In turn, N. M. Vasylytsiv [2] considers digital advertising as a fundamental element of modern communication infrastructure, indicating a change in approaches to interaction with the consumer. These works form a methodological basis for further applied research.

Empirical aspects of digital advertising are highlighted in the work of S. S. Hrynkevich, Zh. D. Sorokina and M. A. Sitarchuk [3], who, using sociological methods, demonstrate the effectiveness of targeted advertising, which has significant practical significance for marketing strategies in social networks. In parallel, O. V. Deinega and I. O. Deinega [4] turn to strategic trends, identifying current directions in the development of advertising policy: personalization, mobility and CRM integration, which reflects the shift in focus to analytics and process automation. Considerable attention is paid to the barriers to implementing digital advertising in the publication of O. M. Yeremenko and I. I. Liashko [5]. The authors analyze the socio-economic determinants that inhibit the digital development of advertising in Ukraine, particularly enterprises' insufficient level of digital literacy. Scientists O. V. Kniazieva, I. V. Muntian, R. R. Znachek considered the methodology of advertising market research for effective advertising, which helps marketers create the correct positioning and expression of the company's brand [6]. A similar topic is raised by N. E. Kuzio and N. S. Kosar [7], emphasizing the weak analytical support of Internet marketing and the fragmentation of communication channels. The publications of M. V. Malchyk and I. P. Adasiuk [8], as well as O. A. Pidlisna and A. O. Vybornov [9], outline the processes of the evolution of advertising in social networks and the specifics of promoting business pages, respectively. These sources deepen the understanding of changing consumer behavioral patterns under the influence of the dynamics of digital platforms. Complementary to them is the review of O. A. Yurchenko [10], which provides a macro analysis of the Ukrainian Internet advertising market, indicating the main

limitations, particularly legislative gaps and lack of strategic vision. A practical orientation is traced in the works of N. O. Derzhak and T. Yu. Zinchenko [11] analyzes cases promoting online services, allowing for the formation of practical recommendations for enterprises. Also valuable is the international dimension presented in the publication by S. Zaika et al. [12], which reveals the specifics of the advertising industry's response to the challenges of the pandemic and the intensification of digital competition. For his part, S. Mikadze [13] offers a model for assessing a minimally viable product, which expands the toolset of startups in digital marketing. Finally, the works of L. V. Tiesheva, E. D. Borysenko [14] and Yu. O. Oleksenko O. V. Sydorenko [15] focuses on the internal management processes of advertising activities. It allows us to outline the directions of its optimization in digitalization, particularly through automation and the implementation of IT solutions. Thus, the analyzed publications represent a wide range of topics - from conceptual approaches to advertising effectiveness to institutional and behavioral barriers. However, specific issues, including the standardization of digital communications, a comprehensive assessment of the full name of advertising campaigns, and the ethics of personalized advertising, remain insufficiently addressed and require further research.

Identification of Previously Unresolved Parts of the general problem. In the modern scientific literature on marketing and advertising, aspects related to the integration of outdoor advertising into business expansion strategies in developing markets remain underdeveloped. There are no models for adapting outdoor advertising to consumers' socio-cultural, linguistic and behavioral characteristics in different countries. The effectiveness of outdoor advertising in combination with digital communication channels has not been sufficiently studied, particularly in a fragmented media field. There is also a lack of empirical data on the profitability of investments in outdoor advertising in an environment with limited marketing budgets. In addition, there are no clearly defined criteria for measuring the reach and

impact of outdoor advertising in regions with low density of digital infrastructure. The strategic potential of outdoor advertising for building brand trust in new or underdeveloped consumer niches remains unexplored.

These aspects remain beyond the scope of most studies, focused mainly on digital media or the contexts of developed countries. Their study is necessary to form a holistic picture of marketing strategies capable of ensuring the effective presence of business in promising but difficult-to-reach markets.

Formulation of the article's objectives. This scientific article aims to substantiate the theoretical foundations and develop practical recommendations for the effective integration of outdoor advertising into marketing and advertising strategies for business expansion in developing markets to achieve maximum coverage of the target audience.

Within the framework of the set goal, the following interrelated goals are expected to be achieved:

1. Conduct a critical analysis of modern scientific approaches to outdoor advertising in developing markets.
2. Identify the main factors that affect the effectiveness of outdoor advertising, taking into account local socio-economic and cultural characteristics.
3. Investigate the possibilities of combining outdoor advertising with other marketing channels in conditions of limited digital infrastructure.
4. Develop recommendations for the optimal strategic use of outdoor advertising to increase brand awareness and expand business in new markets.

Achieving these goals will fill the existing scientific gaps in the study of outdoor media's role in communication support for business expansion. It will also contribute to the practical solution of problems related to developing effective marketing strategies in a dynamic environment with limited resources. The validity of the chosen research direction is due to the need to rethink the role of traditional

communication tools in digitalization, which is relevant for both the scientific and applied spheres of marketing management.

Presentation of the main research material. In the context of globalization and the development of marketing technologies, outdoor advertising is gaining particular importance for developing markets. The lack of a stable digital infrastructure, uneven access to the Internet and specific consumer behavior create unique conditions for the formation of effective communication strategies. In the scientific literature, two approaches to outdoor advertising are usually distinguished: traditional and innovative. Traditional is based on classic marketing elements, audience coverage, frequency of message display and visual presence through billboards, city lights, and transport advertising. However, its effectiveness in countries with an unstable regulatory environment, high socio-cultural diversity and limited budgets is often low [1, p. 37].

Innovative marketing approaches focus on integrating digital technologies and personalizing and adapting content in real-time. In developed economies, these tools have already become standard, but in emerging markets, their implementation often faces technical and social constraints, particularly low consumer digital literacy and fragmented infrastructure. Modern research emphasizes the need for a flexible, contextually adapted approach that combines traditional media with digital channels and considers local cultural, economic and behavioral characteristics (table 1). This combination makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of advertising campaigns, make the brand more recognizable and ensure sustainable business development in new markets.

Table 1

Scientific approaches to the use of outdoor advertising in emerging markets

Approach	Characteristics	Advantages	Limitations in emerging markets
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Traditional	Focus on classic media (billboards, transport)	High visibility, ease of implementation	Insufficient adaptation to cultural features; regulatory risks
Digital / Innovative	Using digital billboards, integration with social networks	Personalization, flexibility, analytics	Limited digital infrastructure; low level of digital literacy
Integrated (hybrid)	Combination of traditional and digital methods	Balanced approach, adaptability	Insufficient localization; lack of flexible models for regional features

Source: author's development

It is important to note that most existing research is theoretical or conceptual, while empirical work focused on the specifics of developing markets remains fragmentary and has a limited geographical scope. A significant part of the publications focuses on analyzing general trends in outdoor advertising, rarely considering local features, which significantly reduces the practical value of such conclusions for businesses that strive to work effectively in these conditions [2, p. 92]. In addition, many works do not pay sufficient attention to the issue of measuring the effectiveness of outdoor advertising in the context of developing markets. The applied metrics developed for developed countries do not always reflect the real impact of advertising campaigns in complex socio-economic and technical conditions. The lack of unified and locally adapted criteria makes it difficult to assess results and make informed marketing decisions. Thus, existing scientific approaches do not fully consider the complexity and specificity of developing markets, which creates a need to develop new theoretical models and methodological tools that will increase the effectiveness of outdoor advertising in this segment. It is essential to ensure a comprehensive approach that considers the technical aspects of advertising media and cultural, social and economic factors that significantly affect the perception of advertising messages [3, p. 116].

The experience of using outdoor advertising in developed markets, particularly Europe and the USA, is an essential guideline for the formation of

effective marketing strategies but is not always uniquely adapted to developing markets. In the European Union, outdoor advertising is strictly regulated, ensuring a balance between business interests, society and the urban environment [4, p. 17]. It is integrated into urban culture, which increases audience trust. Digital billboards and interactive screens allow you to quickly adapt content to different target groups, combining traditional and modern technologies for maximum reach. In the USA, outdoor advertising has a more pronounced commercial nature with an emphasis on data analytics, consumer behavior prediction, geolocation, and integration with mobile applications, which increases the effectiveness of advertising campaigns and return on investment. However, there are significant limitations in emerging markets due to several factors. In particular, the low development of telecommunications infrastructure and unstable Internet coverage make it difficult to use digital advertising channels, such as targeted online advertising or platforms with automated campaign management. The regulatory environment is often characterized by a lack of transparent rules of the game, frequent changes in legislation and uneven application of norms in different regions. In addition, socio-cultural features, particularly linguistic diversity, local values and distinctive consumer practices, require flexible, context-adapted strategies. Such strategies usually contradict unified approaches developed based on the experience of the USA and EU markets, which limits the possibility of direct transfer of these models. Therefore, the experience of developed markets requires significant adaptation, considering the local context. It opens up space for further research and development of flexible strategies focused on national, technological and cultural features. It is crucial to form practical marketing approaches that will ensure maximum coverage and competitive advantages for businesses in dynamic and unstable markets [5, p. 60]. Table 2 describes the approaches used in developed markets of Europe and the USA.

Table 2

Characteristics of approaches to outdoor advertising in developed markets

Characteristics	Europe	USA
Regulation	High regulatory regulation, emphasis on aesthetics and integration into the urban environment	Strict commercial regulation focused on efficiency
Technological level	Wide use of digital billboards and interactive screens	Active use of analytics, geolocation, and digital technologies
Content adaptation	Localized messages taking into account cultural features	Dynamic content based on consumer data
Audience orientation	Balance between business interests, society and urban culture	Maximum reach and conversions
Campaign effectiveness	High due to regulation and technology	High due to the use of analytics and adaptation
Key challenges	Balancing commerce and public interests	High competition, rapid changes in consumer behavior

Source: author's development

A comparative analysis of outdoor advertising experience in Europe and the USA shows different approaches to regulation, technology and audience orientation. In Europe, advertising is strictly regulated with an emphasis on aesthetic integration into the urban environment, which increases consumer trust. In the USA, the main attention is paid to commercial efficiency and analytics to adapt content [6, p. 22]. Technologically, Europe widely uses digital billboards, while the USA actively uses geolocation and behavioral analytics. European campaigns balance business interests and social values, while American ones focus on maximum reach and conversion. The challenges of Europe are associated with balancing commerce and society, while the USA is experiencing high competition and rapid changes in consumer behavior. In general, the effectiveness of advertising in both regions is achieved through a combination of regulation, technology and flexibility of marketing strategies [7, p. 90].

The effectiveness of outdoor advertising is a multifaceted phenomenon that depends on numerous factors, among which local socioeconomic and cultural features play a significant role. Studying these factors is necessary to form adapted

marketing strategies that allow for maximum coverage of the target audience and ensure high effectiveness of advertising campaigns [8, p. 130]. The socioeconomic context determines the level of purchasing power, the structure of the consumer market, and the availability of technologies and infrastructure, which affects the choice of outdoor advertising formats, its placement and the frequency of contact with the audience. For example, in regions with a high level of urbanization, digital billboards and interactive screens can be more effective than traditional billboards due to a higher concentration of potential consumers and better technical support. Cultural features have a decisive influence on the perception of advertising messages. They include linguistic nuances, visual symbols, color schemes, social values and norms of behavior [9, p. 170]. Socioeconomic and cultural factors also determine the advertising formats acceptable to the market. In some regions, mobile advertising media are popular, allowing for rapid coverage of large areas, while in others, static billboards at strategically essential points remain more effective [10, p. 12]. The level of education of the population and the degree of digitalization affect the degree to which consumers are ready to perceive interactive technologies and complex visual content. Also, socioeconomic status often correlates with the type of vehicles prevailing in the region, which determines the places for advertising (for example, advertising near public transport stops or highways). Special attention should be paid to the influence of the legal and regulatory environment, which forms the boundaries of what is possible for outdoor advertising in specific conditions. Legislative restrictions, standards and requirements for the appearance of advertising are reflected not only in the design and format of messages but also in the accessibility of advertising spaces [11, p. 2]. In countries with strict regulations, advertisers are forced to find creative solutions that do not violate the norms but at the same time remain attractive to the target audience. It emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach to planning advertising campaigns, considering all local factors.

The relationship between socioeconomic and cultural aspects is often complex and inextricable. Socioeconomic development influences the formation of cultural norms, and culture, in turn, determines social expectations and behavior, which directly affects the effectiveness of marketing communications. It necessitates interdisciplinary research considering sociological, economic, and cultural approaches [12, p. 152]. Table 3 presents the key factors that determine the effectiveness of outdoor advertising.

Table 3

Socioeconomic and cultural factors that determine the effectiveness of outdoor advertising

Indicator	Description and Impact
Purchasing power	Determines the type and frequency of consumer contacts, affects the budget of advertising campaigns
Level of urbanization	Influences the choice of advertising format (digital billboards, static signs)
Technological infrastructure	Determines the possibility of using digital and interactive advertising formats
Cultural norms	Influence the perception of advertising messages, linguistic and visual features
Social values	Forms the audience's expectations regarding the content and form of advertising
Legal regulation	Determines the framework for the placement and content of advertising
Educational level	Influences the complexity and form of advertising messages
Transport structure	Determines locations for advertising (stops, highways, pedestrian zones)

Source: author's development

Key factors for the effectiveness of outdoor advertising require consideration of local socio-economic and cultural characteristics. Purchasing power determines the budget and frequency of contact with consumers, and the level of urbanization affects the choice of advertising format - digital billboards are more effective in cities than static ones - in rural areas. Technological infrastructure limits or expands

the possibilities of using modern formats. Cultural norms and social values shape the perception of advertising, which requires localization of content. Legal regulation determines the permissible formats, placement locations, and content of outdoor advertising, such as a ban on alcohol advertising near schools or restrictions on language design by national laws. The population's educational level affects the choice of linguistic structures, presentation style and complexity of messages. In regions with a lower level of education, simple, visually oriented messages with a clear call to action are more effective. The extent and density of transport infrastructure, particularly the presence of highways, bus stops and pedestrian-congested areas, determine the appropriateness of choosing specific locations for advertising media to maximize coverage. Taking these factors into account makes it possible to form not only formally correct but also meaningfully relevant and effective outdoor advertising strategies adapted to the conditions of the target market. [13, p. 3].

In developing markets, where digital infrastructure is often fragmented or underdeveloped, outdoor advertising takes on a special role as an accessible and effective channel of mass communication. However, its effectiveness increases significantly when integrated with other marketing tools, even in the context of technological limitations. An integrated approach to communication allows you to achieve a synergistic effect when the combination of channels compensates for each of their weaknesses. In conditions of limited digitalization, combining outdoor advertising with traditional media, such as radio, television, and print media, is especially effective. Radio has high penetration, especially in rural areas, and when used synchronously with billboards, it creates a repetition effect, strengthening brand recognition. Television requires more costs but allows you to form an emotional image of the brand and maintain the visual style already presented on the street. Printed materials deepen the target audience's information, especially where the Internet is unavailable or unstable [14, p. 15].

Another promising form is the combination of outdoor advertising with mobile marketing - for example, through SMS mailings or QR codes on billboards. In countries with limited access to the Internet, mobile phones remain the primary means of personal communication. The interaction between outdoor advertising and mobile messages promotes personalization and allows brands to create a two-way connection with the target audience. Simple tools, such as a short number or a promotional code placed on an external medium, can attract users to further actions. In this context, direct marketing activities also play an essential role: promotions, offline events, and BTL (Below-the-Line) activities, which receive preliminary support through outdoor advertising.

The key condition for effective integration is to ensure the content and visual consistency of advertising messages between all communication channels. It involves the unity of key messages, style, graphic elements, color scheme and tone in outdoor advertising, social networks, TV advertising, mobile marketing and other channels. For example, the slogan used on a billboard should be duplicated in online advertising and supported by appropriate visual content on social networks, which forms a holistic perception of the brand and enhances the impact of the advertising campaign. All elements should correspond to a single concept: have common visual elements, slogans, colors, and tone.

Integrating outdoor advertising should also be adapted to specific market characteristics: urbanization, transport infrastructure, the spread of communication means and cultural consumption codes. For example, in densely populated urban areas, digital billboards at traffic junctions can be effective, while in rural areas - billboards along the roads are supplemented by radio and print advertising. In countries with low levels of digital literacy, the simplicity and visual clarity of outdoor advertising are especially valuable, and channels with a deeper context (e.g., print) should reinforce the main message [15, p. 150].

An integrated communication message serves as the core of the communication strategy, around which all advertising activities are formed - from outdoor advertising to digital channels, ensuring content consistency and brand perception integrity (table 4). An integrated approach allows you to achieve reach, relevance and flexibility even in unstable market conditions. It ensures a more rational use of resources, forms stable communication ties with the audience and adapts to the local environment.

Table 4

The role of marketing channels in integration with outdoor advertising in conditions of limited digital infrastructure

Channel	Advantages in conditions of restrictions	Functional interaction with outdoor advertising
Radio	Wide coverage, even in rural areas	Increases message repeatability, creates a sound association
Television	Visual and emotional support	Strengthening the brand through video sequences, consistency of style
Print media	Deep information, local specificity	Supplement of the information component, detailing offers
Mobile Marketing	Accessibility, even without the Internet	Interaction via SMS, QR codes, personalization
Direct activities (BTL)	Direct contact with the target audience	Announcement of events, strengthening trust through personal interaction

Source: author's development

The presented data prove that outdoor advertising achieves maximum effectiveness through integration with traditional media and direct communication channels in conditions of limited digital infrastructure. Radio, television and print media provide additional coverage and deepen the content of the advertising message. Mobile marketing allows you to maintain personalized communication with the target audience even without access to the Internet. Direct activities contribute to the formation of trust through direct interaction. Together, these channels enhance the impact of outdoor advertising, providing better brand

recognition and more effective feedback. Table 5 presents strategic approaches to outdoor advertising in new markets.

Table 5

Strategic approaches to the use of outdoor advertising in new markets

Approach	Description
Geolocation targeting	Choosing locations with a high concentration of target audience
Visual consistency	A unified style with other channels for brand recognition
Cultural adaptation	Considering local norms, language, symbols
Combining with other channels	Reinforcing the message through print media, radio, BTL
Stability and frequency	Constant brand presence to build trust

Source: author's development

Thus, the strategic use of outdoor advertising is a key element for increasing brand awareness and effectively entering new markets, especially in conditions of limited digital infrastructure. Combining geographical accuracy, visual consistency, cultural relevance, and integration with other communication channels significantly enhances marketing. It contributes to forming a sustainable brand, strengthening consumer trust and creating a basis for long-term business development in a new market environment.

Conclusions. The study found that outdoor advertising remains an essential tool for business expansion in emerging markets, especially in conditions of limited digital infrastructure. Its effectiveness depends on adapting strategies to local economic, socio-cultural and technical conditions. Combining outdoor advertising with traditional channels - radio, television, print media, and mobile marketing - allows for compensating digital limitations and ensures a broader target audience coverage. Key factors influencing the effectiveness of advertising in developing markets have been identified, including the level of digital infrastructure, local socio-cultural features and regulatory restrictions. Significant potential for

integrating outdoor advertising with mobile marketing, local media and social networks as tools for expanding reach and increasing consumer influence has been identified.

The formulated practical recommendations include adapting the advertising content to target audiences' linguistic and cultural contexts, coordinating messages between communication channels, prioritizing locations for outdoor advertising, and considering transport accessibility and concentration of target traffic. At the same time, the need for further research into local consumer behavior models and assessing the effectiveness of specific advertising formats in individual regions has been identified. Promising areas include the use of case studies and mixed methods for in-depth analysis and the development of adaptive marketing models that consider the specifics of the infrastructure and cultural environment in developing markets.

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